

EXPLORING THE BEST PRACTICES OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS ON SCHOOL-BASED MANAGEMENT

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 10

Pages: 977-997

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2026

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12713641

Manuscript Accepted: 06-08-2024

Exploring the Best Practices of Secondary Schools on School-Based Management

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Abstract

This study focused on the best-practices performed on School-Based Management of public secondary school principals, SBM coordinators and community stakeholders with Advanced Level of Practice (Level - III) in School-Based Management in the Schools Division of Quezon. The researcher used purposive sampling technique in selecting the target respondents. A semi-structured questionnaire was used as a research instrument to gather the data. The study revealed the practices performed in leadership and governance includes schools planning. They set clear vision and define goals and objectives followed by strategic planning for future projects through collaboration. They continuously monitor and evaluate all the projects to ensure success or adjust if problems and issues arise. With regards to governance, they involve of community, internal and external stakeholders through shared governance. The best practices performed in curriculum and learning includes collaborative decision making that involve stakeholders or different organization in all the activities, programs and projects of the school specially if it is about curriculum. They give their time and service, donate, help teachers in projects like in reading and basic math lessons. Furthermore, the schools ensure implementation of the required curriculum practice delegation of task. With the strict monitoring and evaluation, they can also check if everyone is able to adapt in all the trends and innovations of 21st century learning. The best practices performed in accountability and continuous improvement includes review and monitoring to achieve success of continuous improvement and shared accountability. The best practices performed in management of resources includes strict resource allocation which means they value prioritization. Other schools involve their stakeholder. They help teachers for their projects, donate materials or even offer time and skills for manual work. They even help in canvassing, sharing strategies and brainstorming for ways to budget the funds. Moreover, they practice real transparency. Since most schools struggles for budget, schools who look for Income generating Project. The following recommendations were hereby suggested: Division Supervisor may consider to offer refresher courses about SBM and to strengthen stakeholders participation, More detailed guidelines and centralized assistance for school heads and SBM Coordinators, School heads may be consistent in conducting team building among teachers and stakeholders to strengthen their relationship and bonding and for the future researcher to look into considerations the limitations and variable which are not discussed in the paper.

Keywords: *school-based management, best practices*

Introduction

School-Based Management or more commonly referred to as SBM, is the decentralization of decision-making authority from the Government to the local levels and its' stakeholders, such as students, teachers, principals, parents, and communities to ensure a more effective school administration and better accountability of staff. SBM is also referred to as school-based governance, school self-management, or school site management. It fosters demand and ensures that schools provide the social and economic benefits that best reflect the priorities and values of the local communities (Alyami & Floyd 2019).

School-Based Management is an offer of a new paradigm in the scope of education, which provides broad autonomy at the school level (community involvement) within the framework of National Education policy. Autonomy is given to managing resources and funding sources according to priority needs and being more responsive to local needs (Widyastuti et al., 2020).

The granting of broad autonomy to schools is the government's concern for the fluctuating social dynamics in society and efforts to improve the quality of education by the school context. This effort encourages schools with their tips for organizing effective, efficient, and productive learning and education by accommodating various resources for the benefit of students. Community involvement is intended to better understand, assist, and control education management.

Likewise, Amon (2021) The success of the principal is shown through his role, especially as a manager, administrator, and leader Vally and Daud, (2015). In addition to the principal, the success of SBM also lies in the role of the teacher (Lasno, Suriansyah, & Saleh, 2019), because teacher involvement in decision making is the key to the success of schools in implementing SBM.

The implementation of School-Based Management (SBM) is one of the government programs in an effort to improve the quality of education, a problem that often occurs, namely maintaining this government program for a long period of time, Pratiwi (2021). In fact, West Nusa Tenggara as a relatively poor area with HDI levels which is 32nd out of 33 provinces in Indonesia has more severe education problems than other regions in Indonesia. Some factors inhibiting the improvement of the quality of education in NTB, among others: 1) economic factors or poverty, 2) community culture, 3) education system, 4) competence of education personnel, 5) limited facilities, 6) and work culture.

Global public education has sparked recurring trends in which the focus on school administration switched from centralization to decentralization under the impact of contemporary management in industrial and commercial organizations opined (Zajda & Gamage, 2009; Caldwell, 2005 as cited by Roque, 2023). Various school reform movements, all of which attempted to improve efficiency, equity, and quality of education, were introduced as a result of dissatisfaction with the central approach to education and the shift toward decentralization. Many academics agree that the transfer of decision-making power to school levels through the shift to School Based Management (SBM) has been one of the most important innovations in the present reorganization of educational systems.

Education leaders and policy makers are always seeking for reforms to improve the quality of basic education in their country (Villanueva & Dela Cruz 2019). However, despite these initiatives of leading people towards literacy, every institution is still facing its own problems that need to be addressed. These problems, especially in the public school, encompass high dropout rate, quality educational service, high repetition rate, and limited holding capacity of the schools (Abulencia, 2012).

Various efforts have been made to improve the quality of education through effective education but have not achieved optimal results. It is especially true for school principals in remote areas. Principals generally carry out school management based on personal experience following the concepts of thought they have. Principals face various problems, including the lack of disciplined educators and the lack of principal communication with educators and teaching staff. In addition, the problem of facilities and infrastructure is also faced by schools so that the teaching and learning process is less effective, and the principal still faces several other problems. If these problems are left unchecked, they will hurt the quality of education. Therefore, what can be used as a benchmark for principals in leading schools is increasing the quality of education. Good school management is needed to achieve a good school (Wati & Trihantoyo, 2020).

According to Acibar and Pepito (2019) School-Based Management is the decentralization of decision-making authority to schools. At the school level, school heads, teachers and pupils work together with the community leaders and local government officials and other stakeholders to improve school performance. Decentralization, in the context of SBM, is the transfer of responsibility for planning school improvement, raising, allocating and managing resources from the central, regional and division levels down to the school sites (DepED Order NO. 230, series 1999).

Furthermore, the approach of school-based management aims to advance the school educational system. It intends to support DepEd in attaining its mission, vision, and goals. Additionally, it identifies the school principal's strengths and flaws, laying the groundwork for future improvement and affecting the school head's performance (Pepito & Acibar, 2019). The Department of Education initiatives are aimed at continual improvement in education. During school-based management implementation, school heads have a big role in adequately implementing the programs in school-based management. Therefore, every school principal must possess good qualities, strong leadership skills, effective styles that can encourage and stimulate teachers, parents, stakeholders, and students to flourish in their dedication and relationship as a leader (Aba-a, 2010).

In a wider perspective, proper implementation of SBM among public elementary and secondary schools allows competent individuals to make decisions that will improve learning and give the entire school community a voice in key decisions. Likewise, it focuses on accountability for decisions which will lead to greater creativity in the design of programs and redirects resources to support the goals developed in each school. Further, this will lead to realistic budgeting as parents and teachers become more aware of the school's financial status, spending limitations, and the cost of its programs; and improve morale of teachers and nurture new leadership. The programs, projects and activities (PPAs) of schools are expected to be realized through community engagement and partnership. Hence, there is a need to determine the SBM's best practices of some schools which can be benchmarked by others. (FTAD RO1, 2022, P. 3).

Hence, best practices are activities, processes and methods that have helped schools meet or exceed their targets in student performance. They are proven efficient, sustainable, and replicable. The teachers, school heads, district supervisors, division officials, DepEd central bureaus, and the parents and other community stakeholders can scout the best practices via vital signs of improving schools such as significant rise in students' performance levels, academic achievement and participation, completion, retention, and survival rates. (Retrieved from Regional Memo No. 77, s.2022).

Research Questions

This study aimed to discover the best practices on school-based management of selected secondary school principals, SBM coordinators and community stakeholders in the First and Fourth Districts of Quezon, Division of Quezon. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. educational attainment;
 - 1.5. years of working experience; and
 - 1.6. industry/sector?
2. What best practices did you perform in leadership and governance that made your school standout and reach the advanced

- phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM)?
3. What best practices did you perform in curriculum and learning that made your school stand out and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM)?
 4. What best practices did you perform in accountability and continuous improvement that made your school stand out and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM)?
 5. What best practices did you perform in management of resources that made your school stand out and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM)?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed descriptive qualitative research as its design that focused on discovering the best practices of secondary school principals, SBM coordinators and community stakeholders in the implementation of School-Based Management.

Regoniel (2023) Descriptive qualitative research is a method of research that is focused on understanding a phenomenon by examining its characteristics and qualities. This research design was used to explore and understand the characteristics and qualities of a phenomenon. This type of research wanted to explore a topic that was not studied before or wanted to gain a better understanding of a previously studied topic but using a different perspective. Descriptive qualitative research was a type of qualitative research that explored the characteristics of a phenomenon, rather than explaining the underlying causes or mechanisms. It involved the collection and data analysis in the form of words, images, or other non-numerical forms of information.

Hardiansyah (2022) a graduate of Master of Education Management at FKIP Satya Wacana Christian University in Central Java, Indonesia who conducted a study “The Implementation of School-Based Management in Improving Quality of Education in Primary School” where he used the qualitative approach in the form of descriptive qualitative research.

The qualitative method is a research procedure that produces data in written or spoken words from the observed people and actors (Ulfathmi et al., 2021).

This research approach deepened understanding of the nature and the meaning of everyday experiences.

Participants

The target participants of this study were the three (3) secondary school principals, three (3) SBM coordinators and three (3) community stakeholders of schools with Advanced School-Based Management Level of Practice (Level - 3) based on DepEd Quezon Memo. No. 216, s. 2022. The nine (9) participants of this study served as the focus of this study and source of information. The participants in this study were from First and Fourth Districts of Quezon Province.

The school’s participants in this study were two (2) from Fourth District and one (1) from the First District of Quezon Province. These were Perez National High School, Alabat Island National High School and Talipan National High School.

Perez National High School was formerly known as Perez Quezon Academy, a private institution. It was founded by former Municipal Mayor Constancia G. Reyes on July 01, 1949. It is located at Loen Guinto St. Barangay Mapagmahal in the center of the municipality of Perez. Through Republic Act 8006, PQA was converted into Perez National High School March 27, 1996.

At present, the school is headed by Ms. Sighlie M. Regodon, Secondary School Principal II with 43 teaching personnels and 5 non-teaching personnels and 1100 students approximately.

Alabat Island National High School was formerly known as Alabat Municipal High School. On August 2, 1948, the first municipality high school came into reality, founded by Dr. Felix Alpay. This school’s change in a public secondary school located at Brgy Camangong, Alabat, Quezon. It is considered as the largest schools in the island of Alabat. It is composed of 87 Junior High School Teachers and 26 Senior High School Teachers and 7 Non-Teaching Personnels. It is one of the largest schools in Fourth District of Quezon. The school is under the supervision of Mr. Joseph C. Hinanay, Principal IV. The school has thousands of students and it is considered as mega large school category. The school considered as a top performing school in the division of Quezon.

Talipan National High School is a Secondary School located at Sitio Fori, Brgy. Talipan, Pagbilao, Quezon. It is composed of 96 Junior High School Teachers and 25 Senior High School Teachers and 6 Non-Teaching Personnels. It is one of the largest schools in First District of Quezon. The school is under the supervision of Dr. Luningning R. Mendoza. The school has thousands of students and it is considered as mega large school category. Moreover, the school produces quality students that won and exceled in different fields. The school also won different school competitions like Brigada Eskwela, School-Based Management, Campus paper and many more. In addition, the teachers also exceled and won in different fields and competitions.

The researcher selected the target schools with commendable performance in SBM. These schools implemented effective strategies and practices that provided valuable insights for this research study. By focusing on schools with good performance in SBM, researcher gained valuable insights into the effectiveness of this approach in improving educational outcomes.

These schools were likely to implement effective mechanisms, such as collaborative decision-making, teacher empowerment, community involvement, embraced research and innovation, transparency and accountability of actions. By studying these schools, researcher identified best practices and generated evidence-based management.

Moreover, selected schools with good performance in School-Based Management ensured that the participants had knowledge and experiences in the implementation of SBM. These things contributed to the richness and validity of the research findings.

However, the researcher selected the three (3) Secondary School Principals of each school as research participants. In the realm of School-Based Management, the role of a school principal as a leader was crucial in ensuring effective governance and the overall success of educational institutions.

Secondary School Principals as leaders of School Based Management were faced with numerous tasks. Firstly, they possessed strong visionary and strategic planning and skills to set attainable goals for the institution. By setting clear expectations and objections, the School Principal provided a roadmap for the school's progress and growth. Additionally, they demonstrated effective communication skills that foster positive relationship to the students, teachers, parents and other community stakeholders.

Moreover, the principals' responsibility extended to the implementation of various policies and procedures that maintained a well-structured school environment. They exhibited strong organizational and management skills that ensured that resources both human and material were utilized efficiently. Thus, school principals fostered a culture of collaboration and teamwork among all individuals and strived for continuous improvement in all aspects of school operations.

School SBM coordinators played a pivotal role in the implementation of School-Based Management. they were entrusted with responsibility of leading and guiding their colleagues, students and other stakeholders towards achieving the shared vision and goals of the institution. SBM coordinators actively engaged in decision-making processes, such as curriculum development, resource allocation and policy formulation, seeking input from various stakeholders to ensure the best interest of the students and the entire school community. Additionally, they served as a vital link between the administration and faculty, effectively mediating between perspectives that created harmonious environment.

Furthermore, they demonstrated effective communication skills that allowed them to articulate ideas and actively listen to the concerns and feedback of others. They possessed a strong sense of responsibility, readily embracing change and seeking innovative solutions to overcome emerging challenges. With their experiences and knowledge practices, SBM coordinators provided invaluable insights into curriculum design and instructional strategies that aligned the diverse needs of students.

Moreover, School-Based Management coordinators as leaders promoted a culture of professionalisms and continuous learning, encouraging their colleagues to engage in professional development activities and reflective practices to improve the implementation of School-Based Management.

Lastly, in the context of a research study focusing on school-based management, community stakeholders played a crucial role as research-participants. Their active participation and collaboration with schools offered insight into the partnerships established for educational initiatives. By examining their role in providing resources such as internships, donations or volunteer opportunities, the study gained a comprehensive understanding of the local community involvement in shaping educational programs.

Furthermore, community stakeholders participated in shaping policies and decisions that governed schools. The participants contributed to the decision-making process by providing valuable insights and perspectives based on their experiences based on the needs of schools.

Moreover, community stakeholders brought real-world perspectives and expertise to the table, helping the school tailored programs that met the needs of local community and prepared for the future growth of schools and students. The participants active participation ensured that the school system was responsive to the needs of the community and provided students with the best possible learning opportunities.

As a primer mover of School-Based Management, the School Principal, School SBM coordinator and Community stakeholders were the participants of this study. Each participant was asked with a semi-structured question to discover their best practices on School-Based Management.

The researcher used purposive sampling technique in selecting the target respondents. Gallego (2022) Purposeful sampling is a technique widely used in qualitative research for the identification and selection of information-rich cases for the most effective use of limited resources. This involves identifying and selecting individuals or groups of individuals that are especially knowledgeable about or experienced with a phenomenon of interest (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). In addition to knowledge and experience, Bernard (2002) noted the importance of availability and willingness to participate, and the ability to communicate experiences and opinions in an articulate, expressive, and reflective manner.

Moreover, the researcher had an advance information about the target school head-respondents that were near in the researcher's residency. Said respondents in the Division of Quezon were willing to share their best practices to others school.

Procedure

These were some ethical aspects which needed to be considered by the researcher during the conduct of this study. The researcher wrote a permission letter to conduct the study to the Schools Division Superintendent of Quezon Province through data sharing privacy.

After approving the letter, the researcher proceeded to the selected secondary school principals. The researcher also forwarded a letter to inform that they were be the target respondents of this study.

In addition, the researcher informed the respondents about the privacy and confidentiality of their identities as respondents of this research. Upon approval and meeting the salient ethical aspects of the study, the researcher proceeded to the implementation of data collection methods.

Furthermore, the researcher conducted an interview to the selected secondary school principals, SBM coordinators and community stakeholders using the semi-structured interview guide questions. Another way to collect data was by asking the target participants a set of open-ended questions. In conducting interview, the researcher set an interview schedule to the target respondents. This was done in the months of August and September.

However, the researcher asked the availability of the respondents to conduct an interview. As part of this study, the researcher made a scheduled interview with the target participants. The researcher visited the respondents' location to interview personally. The researcher might opt to use the online platforms like google meet and zoom to interview the respondents depending on the preferred mode of interview or the availability of the respondents. Electronic materials like cellphone, laptop was used to gather information in recording and interviewing the respondents.

Data Analysis

This study used thematic analysis method of data analysis. This approach helped the researcher to interpret qualitative data. According to Jack Caulfield (2022) Thematic analysis is a method of analyzing qualitative data. It is usually applied to a set of texts, such as interviews or transcriptions. The researcher closely examines the data to identify common themes, topics, ideas and patterns of meaning that come up repeatedly. Thematic analysis is an increasingly popular method to analyze qualitative data that captures patterns across the raw data and structures the data into meaningful themes (Braun et al., 2019; Campbell et al., 2021).

After the interview, the researcher transcribed the respondents' answers. This started to articulate and scrutinize the data and started to create themes and coding. The researcher grouped the similar categories and organized them into themes. Moreover, the results were interpreted into a comprehensive description.

However, the data analysis technique in this study used the Miles and Huberman strategy, which consisted of data reduction, data display and conclusion drawing/verification (Moleong, 2019). The researcher simplified by sorting out the data to be used, while the irrelevant data meant that the data was not used. After simplifying the data, the data were grouped according to the indicators in the study. Next, the researcher presented the data obtained as a research report.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were exercised in the development of this study. This covered the approval of Schools Division Superintendent of DepEd Quezon to conduct this research study. Upon approval, the researcher disseminated a letter to conduct to the selected secondary school principals and a letter of consent that they freely gave their time and efforts to be a part of this study. The researcher gave an overview about the study and why they were the target respondents. An informed consent letter was discussed also as part of this study to protect participants confidentiality before the data collection. To maximize the confidentiality, the responses of the target respondents were not shared with anyone. The coding technique was used to hide their real identity. This was also used in the transcription of data. The collected records were preserved for five (5) years before being destroyed.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and analysis of the gathered data based on the presented guide questions in the study.

Demographic profile of the participants.

Table 1 presents the profile of the participants who are composed of, school heads, SBM coordinator and stakeholders.

It can be gleaned on the table that the first participant is 51-55 years old, female, single and has Ph.D units. She is in the institutions for 31-35 years old and belong to education sector. The second participant is 46-50 years old, female and married. He is a MAEd graduate and serving the institution for 26-30 years and belong to education sector. The third participant is 31-35 years old, female, married and a Diploma graduate. She is serving the institution for 6-10 years in LGU/government. The fourth participant is a 56 and above years old, male, married and has Ph.D Units. He is serving the institution for 36-40 and belong to an education sector. The fifth participant is 36-40, female, married and a MAEd Graduate, she is serving the institution for 11-15 in an education sector. The sixth participant is 31-35, male, single and a Bachelor Graduate. He is serving the institution for 11-15 years in LGU/Gov't. The seventh participant is 41-45years old, female, married and Ph.D Graduate. She is serving the institution for 21-25years in an Education sector.

The eighth participant is 51-55 years old, female, married and with Ph.D Units. She is serving the institution for 31-35 years in Education sector. The ninth participant is 41-45, female, married and a Bachelor Graduate. She is serving the institution for 21-25 in LGU/Gov't.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the participants

Participant	Age	Sex	Civil status	Educ. Attainment	Work experience	Industry/ sector
1	51-55	Female	Single	Ph.D Units	(31-35)	Education
2	46-50	Male	Married	MAEd Graduate	(26-30)	Education
3	31-35	Female	Married	Diploma Graduate	(6-10)	LGU/Gov't
4	56 Above	Male	Married	Ph.D Units	(36-40)	Education
5	36-40	Female	Married	MAEd Graduate	(11-15)	Education
6	31-35	Male	Single	Bachelor Graduate	(11-15)	LGU/Gov't
7	41-45	Female	Married	Ph.D Graduate	(21-25)	Education
8	51-55	Female	Married	Ph.D Units	(31-35)	Education
9	41-45	Female	Married	Bachelor Graduate	(21-25)	LGU/Gov't

It can be implied that the School Heads, SBM coordinators and stakeholders who are actively involved in SBM are seasoned and well-experienced in serving the school and community. They are in the most suitable age to serve and to work in the field. They are already responsible, matured and accountable in all the task that may be given to them.

This is supported by Aya et al. (2022) revealed the findings that public elementary schools have shared and participatory processes for determining stakeholders' roles, responsibilities, and accountability in managing and supporting education. Caño et al. (2021) support the results by emphasizing that education is a shared responsibility, and it takes a village to educate a child.

Best practices performed in leadership and governance that made the school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM)

The table below shows the statement of the participants and its theme and category. This presents the sharing of the school heads, SBM Coordinators and stakeholders with regards to their best practices performed in leadership and governance that made the school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM).

Table 2. Best practices performed in leadership and governance that made the school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM)

Theme	Sub-Theme	Category	Responses
Planning	Clear vision and set goals and objectives	Leadership	<p>P1- In leadership and governance leader must develop a clear vision and mission for the school. We have to set a goal for what is good for the school. For example is strategic planning so we have to plan to facilitate the development of vision and mission for the future of the school. I think sir planning is really important and involvement of stakeholders because they really contributed for the improvement of the school.</p> <p>P5- in our school we have the practice of planning, we start everything in planning. It is made possible by collaborative work of stakeholders. We have development plan, these are the school programs, the PPAs , they are part of the planning in our SIP the school improvement plan. The stakeholders are part of the planning, we have representatives from LGU the local government unit and different personnel.</p>
Shared Governance	Involvement of community stakeholders	Governance	<p>P2- In shared governance not only the school who manages the school operation alone, we invite the stakeholders in managing school operations, we create a school management team, we have BOD the board of directors or from the PTA or the parent-teacher association and also the SGC and SPT another group from stakeholders. The participation of every member of the school has a great impact for the success of project and program in the school, we are not only the prime movers but also the stakeholders who shared their feedback and suggestions for the improvement of school.</p> <p>P4- The best weapon to reach the highest level, is the shared governance. Where in every single unit of the schools. All stakeholders, internal and external stakeholders, are involved in planning involved in the implementation involved in controlling whatever Project, Activity program, practicing activities that will be undertaken by the school.</p>
Collaboration	Open communication by sharing of ideas and suggestions	Leadership	<p>P3- We express our sides to know that or what they need, and the LGU can make a solution. we have sharing of ideas and suggestions we have collaboration in decision making, we shared what we know and we practice that every meeting in the LGU and we applied in the school, lalo pag my plan and school sa mga project nila ay nasheshare naming ung mga practices namin.</p> <p>P6- We have the sharing of opinions to another and give feedback, we also practice that when we have school meeting because the voice of everyone is important for the improvement of school.</p>

			<p>P7- I practice the active collaboration to everyone that is why I always invite them to join in every activity, So the decisions and suggestions are shared by every Member and by every Member, and maybe from the school and the Community. And then so that they can help in planning all members of the school community feel valued and respected. And then of. Course, this working together promotes common goals. To reach in achieving the desired outcomes.</p> <p>P9- Let us have the open communication the school and stakeholders practice the sharing of opinions or suggestion when we have a meeting we all explain and give suggestions in our meeting, like in project implementation we give suggestions.</p>
Monitoring and Evaluation	Continuity	Leadership	<p>P8-By implementing old projects with continuous monitoring. Evaluation and make sure that the best result. Continuous talk with all the stakeholders on how they can be part of our leadership and our by asking the help of.</p>

For the school heads, the best practices that they performed to show best leadership and governance which that made the school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM) include: P1 stated that “Leader must develop a clear vision and mission for the school. A good leader should possess a clear vision and set goals and objectives accordingly. This help provide the direction and purpose for the entire school. Like leading strategically is one of the qualities that every leader must display. We have to set a goal for what is good for the school. We should know what we want to see the school for the future. For example, strategic planning so we have to plan to facilitate the development of vision and mission for the future of the school. We also need the active participation of stakeholders. I encourage all the members of the school to join for the discussion of school mission and vision. I always set a clear vision and mission for a school. It will start in planning before you move we have to think what works best for the school and it is not enough that you are the one who will work for that. P4 said that “The best weapon to reach the highest level, is the shared governance. Where in every single unit of the schools. All stakeholders, internal and external stakeholders, are involved in planning involved in the implementation involved in controlling whatever Project, Activity program, practicing activities that will be undertaken by the school. The participation of all person, and person inside the school. One concrete example is the. Creation of the School Governance Council, which composed of the school head, the president of PTA, the President of the Student government, the President of Alumni from the state from external stakeholder, the President of. The President of personal club or Association of Teachers, so that that committee, the function of the committee, is to oversee the total operations of the school. When it when it comes to financial management. The same strategy shared governance wherein. You have to organize another committee like bids in our Community inspector, Inspection Inspector Inspectorate committee. And participation.” And lastly for P7 “You know, in building a leadership practice, it’s important to encourage everyone. Thank you, mam. In collaboration and of. Course being more in every program or project. So we should involve. The School, of course, and especially most especially the community stakeholders in planning. Then they practicing, practicing collaboration and doing more. So the decisions and suggestions are shared by every Member and by every Member, and maybe from the school and the Community. And then so that they can help in planning all members of the school community feel valued and respected. And then of. Course, this working together promotes common goals. To reach in achieving the desired outcomes. As a school head, we should build a strong leadership practice, you have you to everyone that you are good leader by example. One thing is that you need to practice a good leadership showing that you can lead people in accomplishing goals because it is important that you can encourage everyone to participate in every activity. I practice the active collaboration to everyone that is why I always invite them to join in every activity, by means of that you show your leadership because they follow you.”

For the SBM Coordinators, P2 stated that “We practice shared governance in managing school operation, of course, and this type of governance ensures that. It’s not only the internal stakeholders, holders or the teachers and the school administrators involved, but of course. Regarding the operation, we also include or enjoy these external stakeholders as well. And we believe that involvement in the wider community in this school operation. Facilitates finding the problems in school and solving easier than through teamwork and shared responsibility. So we believe that with the help of parents and the external stakeholders, the best practices of the school was OK. We invite the stakeholders in managing school operations, we create a school management team, we have BOD the board of directors or from the PTA or the parent-teacher association and also the SGC and SPT another group from stakeholders. As you all know the participation of all members in the shared governance contributed in the progress of the school, for example if the school is planning to launch or plan a program or project the school not only do the decisions for the implementation and monitoring but also the stakeholders they participated actively they shared their ideas for the improvement because there are thing that they know or thing that can contribute for the improvement of the school.” P5 shared that “Everything starts from planning, so the development plan, which is all the programs, the projects and PPA’s are included. We have the AIP. We have the SIP. Which is it is collaborative work by the stakeholders. So we have representatives from LGU, we have the school planning team and coming from the LGU and not only from but different stakeholders including of course the personnel. Here and with that. I can say that the stakeholder’s participation is really number one, number one or the major contributor for that for the implementation of this best practices of the school because without them, of course it cannot be. P8 said that “We made our school standout for the for the best practices, as other schools do, by implementing old projects with continuous monitoring. Evaluation and make sure that the best result. By means of continuous. So when it comes to leadership, when I say continuous talk is the direction of the school to prepare for some leadership trainings and seminars that will contribute to the progress of the school, meaning to say there are a lot of. Topics to be discussed in the trainings and seminars in the leadership of, say, principal and then those are those things that can be learned.

For the stakeholders, P3 said that “As community stakeholder, we practice coaching and mentoring to one another in order to achieve goals or objectives. In this activity, we can improve or achieve relationships towards school development like we do in our sharing our opinions or suggestions. And there is a meeting in school. During the activity, we express our sides to know that or what they need, and the LGU can make a solution. we have sharing of ideas and suggestions, when the principal called us that we have a meeting we attended and we have discussion for example the school will make a project, we share the knowledge of what we have because it is important to know the side of everyone” P6 shared that, “I think in leadership we we perform giving feedback and suggestions to one another to achieve the mission, vision and goals, we practice sharing of opinions and it can help to us. in giving feedback and suggestion we apply that in school meeting, you that in school meeting of course everyone is encouraged to give our suggestions and opinions, sa ganoong pagkakataon naiisahre naming ang mga bagay na alam naming, for example pag ang school ay mayroong project nagagawin, pinakikita naming ang aming support s school projects we shared suggestions for the improvement of project. it is good to share opinions to everyone so that we have many choices o options na pwede natin pagpilian para s improvement nga ng school. Open communication talaga ang dapat lagi natin ipractice sa bawat bagay.” While P9 said that “The most important thing is. Open communication and collaboration. We create communication like us. We are stakeholders, we feel comfortable to express our opinions or ideas. We share it. If there is a meeting or problems. Let us have the open communication the school and stakeholders practice the sharing of opinions or suggestion when we have a meeting we all explain and give suggestions in our meeting, like in project implementation we give suggestions. We join in school meeting during the meeting we have exchanging of ideas in planning for school project. we have the culture of being open to everyone and that we like to each member of school.”

It can be inferred from the interview that the best practices performed in leadership and governance that made the school stand out and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM) vary in different school. With regards to leadership, the first theme is planning wherein the school sets clear vision and define goals and objectives with the stakeholders. From this vision, goals and objectives strategic planning for future projects followed which are all aligned with the mission, vision, and needs of the school. The school, together with the stakeholders, plan for activities, programs and projects that will ensure development and will benefit the learners, community and the school itself. This planning will start from setting the objectives or goals which are all align with the mission and vision of the school and the needs of the school. These objectives will serve as basis in crafting activities, projects and programs which are all learner-centered, focusing on school improvement and extending their horizon with the stakeholders. This is based on the statement of P1 which is: “In leadership and governance leader must develop a clear vision and mission for the school. A good leader should possess a clear vision and set goals and objectives accordingly. We have to set a goal for what is good for the school. We should know what we want to see the school for the future. For example, is strategic planning so we have to plan to facilitate the development of vision and mission for the future of the school.”

This is further supported by Karmila and Wijaya, (2020) who stated that vision, mission, and objectives are the foundations to implement the school-based management against the ordinary system. Vision and mission are set by the cooperation of principal, teachers, and school committee. The preparation of the vision and mission was followed by socialization to let all school members understand the outlines of vision and mission.

The second theme is collaboration wherein everyone has equal chance to share and contribute ideas and work together to help improve school. This collaboration stimulates open communication among the people involve since each member is given a chance to share their ideas, give comments and suggestions and voice out their feedbacks for the benefit of the school and learners. Moreover, these feedbacks my serve as a basis for improvements since school will be able to reflect and evaluate the programs and projects of the school. This collaboration among the school, internal stakeholders and external stakeholders start from the planning which is extended into implementation and monitoring to ensure proper implementation and success. Moreover, they extend also help in manual work to assist the school. This is based on the statement of P3: We have sharing of ideas and suggestions we have collaboration in decision making, we shared what we know and we practice that every meeting in the LGU and we applied in the school, lalo pag my plan and school sa mga project nila ay nasheshare naming ung mga practices namin. We shared opinions for the improvement of the school like what I said during the meeting that is a good work for us. And that is.

This is in relation to roles of community of SBM system. They cooperate with teachers and principal in teaching, learning, campus development, school activities, and so forth. In the traditional ways, parents are not allowed to influence or to make decision in the key school-level matters such as teacher training, teacher hiring and firing, pedagogy, etc. (Santibañez et al., 2014). Community involvement can be divided into several portions such as planning committee, documentation committee, food and snacks committee, evaluation committee, and so on (Pepito & Acibar, 2019). External stakeholder participation can be cooperated with joint managements under school management system. Parent monitoring has been received as an effective tool to administer the school level inputs.

The next theme is monitoring and evaluation which focus on close monitoring and constant evaluation of programs and projects which are all on going. As the school pioneered their programs and projects, it is very important that they continuously monitor and evaluate all the projects to ensure success or adjust if problems and issues arise. School heads and SBM coordinators play vital role in monitoring and evaluating the programs and projects which can be presented to external stakeholders for feedbacking to hear their comments and suggestions. Through this, they will be able to look into consideration the other aspects of all the activities, programs and projects. This is based on the statement of P8: “We made our school stand out for the for the best practices, as other schools do, by implementing old projects with continuous monitoring. Evaluation and make sure that the best result.”

This is further supported by Tansiri and Bong (2019) who stated that school-based management (SBM) is an effective way of enhancing participatory decision-making, budgetary transparency, and community participation.

With regards to governance, the theme is shared governance because the participants believe that they are in their best if they practice shared governance wherein everyone is involved in the process of overseeing the control and direction of the school. They involve the community, internal and external stakeholders in planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation. Through shared governance everyone holds responsibility and contributes to the progress of the school. Involvement of everyone in every activity is visible and commendable since they devote their time and exerted effort for the school. This is based on the statement of P2: We practice shared governance in managing school operation, of course, and this type of governance ensures that. It's not only the internal stakeholders, holders or the teachers and the school administrators involved, but of course. Regarding the operation, we also include or enjoy these external stakeholders as well. And we believe that involvement in the wider community in this school operation. Facilitates finding the. Problems in school and solving easier than through teamwork and shared responsibility. So we believe that with the help of parents and the external stakeholders, the best practices of the school was okay”.

This result is supported by Seryanti et al. (2021) key leadership has a relevant and concrete effect on school-based management in improving efficiency. The principal's leadership plays an important role in overseeing the administration of education to efficiently and effectively meet school goals. Educational advancement can be made through changes and improvements in school education management (Fathurrochman et al., 2019).

Best practices that school perform in curriculum and learning that made them standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM)

The table below shows the statement of the participants and its theme and category. This presents the sharing of the school heads, SBM Coordinators and stakeholders with regards to the best practices that school perform in curriculum and learning that made them standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM)

Table 3. *Best practices that school perform in curriculum and learning that made them standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM)*

Theme	Sub-Theme	Category	Responses
Collaborative decision making	Involvement of stakeholders or different organization	Curriculum	P1- We practice the collaborative decision making. The involvement of different organization in the community and contributes a lot in planning for the improvement of the curriculum as students are the center of education. And school-based management involves the active participation of every member. P2- the involvement of community stakeholders in the school operation, involves the community and planning implementation of the projects P9- is by engaging the parents and the stakeholders in curriculum decisions, inviting the parents to be a part of the planning. And implement the implementation of project of school.
Quality Learning	Designed programs	Learning	P2- We created projects and programs for students at risks, students who are in need of educational assistance and many more P5- we have Implemented the different programs or projects and activities which helps our learners develop, develop their skills, develop their personality.
Assistance	Participation	Curriculum	P3- We took part in developing learning programs that are suited to learner's context. We give more attention to schools needs like giving financial assistance or supplies. We also participate in Brigada Pagbasa as one of the schools activities and we help the students to make sure that they can read. Yes sir, we also give assistance to the students like we have the project GTS or grant transportation subsidy we give assistance to those students who are facing problem in transportation P6- We support the programs or projects of school. Like giving funds or materials, even if it's small .
Implementation	Delegation	Curriculum	P4- We are practicing the process of delegation. It is impossible for a single school head to manage the curriculum in this very large school, in order to make sure that the effective learning will happen we organize the staff aside from department heads, we have coordinators by grade levels to monitor the proper. Implementation of. Curriculum and proper execution of the lessons
Adaptability	Changes and improvements Innovation	Curriculum	P7- we are in the 21st century so we have to adapt what is timely relevant nowadays in education for us to improve the quality of education that we can give to our students. I always tell my teachers and to the students let us embrace the changes and innovation in education we have to be flexible because we are in the 21st century education. P8- having continuous innovations and we have come up with some of the contextualized materials

For the school heads, the best practices that school perform in curriculum and learning that made them standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM), P1 stated that “We practice the collaborative decision making. The

involvement of different organization in the community and contributes a lot in planning for the improvement of the curriculum as students are the center of education. We time up and partner to different community organizations. We develop service learning projects that help address needs of the student in learning. The community stakeholders join in our brigade eskwela you can see them helping teachers and other members donating learning materials and they also help students to read they participate in brigada eskwela that we do every time during the enrollment. P4 said that “We are practicing the process of delegation. That it is impossible for a single school head to manage the curriculum in this very large school, in order to make sure that the effective learning will happen you have we have, , we organize the staff we have here the. Department heads aside from department heads, we have coordinators by grade levels. We have assigned in different monitors assigned in different curriculum level in order to ensure the proper. Implementation of. Curriculum and proper execution of the lessons of. The teachers in. Of course, to reach the best standard set by the by the Department of Education, which is the quality education. During the process of delegation, for example, we have all school head, has the supervisory plan, so in order for the school head to monitor all the teachers and determine the extent of the teaching and learning process the part in supervising instruction is delegated to the department Heads.” and for the P7, “We practice course adaptability. And of course, better embrace that flexibility as we accommodate the changing needs of the students and of course, the school community. We all know that the students nowadays are different compared to the old. There is as time goes by. So this will. Be performed by reviewing the programs and projects packs they implemented in the student updates and of course your support form identifying needs of the students as we embrace the innovation and research. That will help to. Improve the curriculum and learning so I adopt the changes to this as the 21st century and we have to be flexible. We really need to give more focus in this component, because there are so many changes and improvements in the curriculum, now we are in the 21st century so we have to adapt what is timely relevant nowadays in education for us to improve the quality of education that we can give to our students.”

For the SBM Coordinator, P2 stated, “The school management involves the community and planning implementation of the projects. As well as in monitoring and evaluation of the success or failure of the programs and projects, and of course the school planning team composed of the school personnel. The community leaders and learners representative developed learning programs and projects that are suited to the community and the learners context there via developing holistic learning among students. We encourage them to be part of the school operation or program but also we give them recognition for their efforts, because we are lucky that they are willing to help as you can see everytime we have school program like brigada eskwela , school beautification program and many more, lagi sila nan jan to support the school, kita naman sa kanila they also give their support to our school program as you know they are willing to help the school and they very active in planning in our meeting o school deliberation of program and project.” P5 said that, “We give more focus on our students’ development and we all know that our students is the center of learning process. our school has different programs and projects for the improvement of our students. We have different projects in English we have the project race we want to sure that every student can read and be a reader and in mathematic we have project numero. we have Implemented the different programs or projects and activities which helps our learners develop, develop their skills, develop their personality.” Lastly, P8 shared that “We have the best practices of having continuous innovations. We have some contextualized materials. In the implementation, the provided materials are being validated in the district level and that is being implemented.

For the stakeholders, P3 stated that “The school talked to us about the help that they need. We give assistance. We took part in developing learning programs that are suited to learner's context. We join in school program like in Brigada Eskwela we are part of the activity and the school invited us. So participated in cleaning and repainting of school . we also participated in Brigada Eskwela we helped the teacher assisting the students to read. nagpabasa kami sa mga bata na nageenrol nakakatuwa at nakakatulong km isa mga bata. We also give assistance to the students like we have the project GTS or grant transportation subsidy we give assistance to those students who are facing problem in transportation.” P6 said that “We support the needs of the schools, especially for the improvement of the students. We support the programs or projects of school. Like giving funds or materials, even if it's small. We give donations and assistance to the schools. Like what we have in opening of classes we donate learning material and school supplies for the students and we support school projects and program, pag meron mga activity like contest nag bibigay kami ng kunting funds for prize or ganun. We give donations during the brigade eskwela, minsan hindi lang basta need ng school o students. Like giving school supplies for the students and also we support school activities for the students.” Lastly, P9 shared that “I think a good way is by engaging the parents and the stakeholders in curriculum decisions. It is also essential for successful learning of the students, inviting the parents to be a part of the planning. And implement the implementation of project of school. It is important that the parents are part of the curriculum decisions because sometime the parents don't know problems in school.”

It can be deduced from the result that the best practices that school perform in curriculum and learning that made them stand out and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM) includes: The first theme is collaborative decision making which focus on the involvement of stakeholders or different organization in all the activities, programs and projects of the school specially if it is about curriculum. The school gives voices and chances among stakeholders to be part of decision making and allow them to share their comments, suggestions, views and opinions in the teaching learning process, activities, projects and programs of the school. Schools are better off if they are supported by stakeholders. Projects and programs will not be successful if they are not supported by parents, LGU and NGO. The decisions of the school become more effective and stronger through the help of the people around them because of their shared discussion, comments, suggestions and feedback. This is based on the statement of P1 who shared that: “We practice the collaborative decision making. The involvement of different organization in the community and contributes a lot in planning for the improvement of the curriculum. In collaborative decision making we all know that the school cannot handle all

program and projects in curriculum and learning especially we have limited funds or resources. We tie up and partner to different community organizations. We develop service learning projects that help address needs of the student in learning.”

This in accordance with De Luna (2021) stated that SBM requires all members of the school community to partake in the decision-making processes concerning budget, curriculum and personnel. With the implementation of SBM, the Department of Education is doing its very effort to create an environment where all the people involved in the decision-making process will be committed to make change happen under a decentralized setup.

The next theme is assistance wherein stakeholders give assistance to schools. They ensure participation in all activities, projects and programs. Stakeholders help the schools during brigada eskwela. They give their time and service as they go to school to help in repair, and cleaning. Moreover, they donate to help provide for the needs of the school. The assistance of the parents does not end in Brigada Eskwelala, it is extended all throughout the year because they also help teachers in projects like in reading and basic math lessons. They also assist or share knowledge in crafting programs and projects. They surely extend help in any way they can. They attend meetings, convergence, conference to be always present. They allot time, man power, and financial assistance to make sure that their presence and help are felt by the school. This is based on the statement of P3 who shared that: “We give assistance. We took part in developing learning programs that are suited to learner's context. We extend our supports for the benefits of students. We give more attention to schools needs like giving financial assistance or supplies. We also participate in Brigada Pagbasa as one of the schools activities and we help the students to make sure that they can read.”

This is in connection with Tansiri and Bong (2019) who shared that to build school relationship with the society, there were several efforts have been done such as forming and empowering schools committee, having a routine meeting with schools committee at the end of semester, obligating the parents to take the rapport of their children every semester, building the relationship with society to be involved actively in the improvement of educational quality, providing information about the school to the society and cultivate the transparency in school management.

Furthermore, the next theme is implementation wherein the schools ensure implementation of the required curriculum especially the programs and projects that are related to the curriculum. This specific theme focuses on strict implementation of crafted programs and projects which are products of collaborative effort of everyone. To make it a success, the school heads delegate the task to subject group heads, department heads and coordinators to strictly implement all the projects and program of the school and eventually monitor and evaluate all aspects of the curriculum. With the strict monitoring and evaluation, they can also check if everyone is able to adapt in all the trends and innovations of 21st century learning. With this they can adjust for the necessary changes and improvements for better service. This is based on the statement of P7 who shared that: “We practice course adaptability. And of course, better embrace that flexibility as we accommodate the changing needs of the students and of course, the school community. We all know that the students nowadays are different compared to the old. There is as time goes by. So this will. Be performed by reviewing the programs and projects packs they implemented in the student updates and of course your support form identifying needs of the students as we embrace the innovation and research. That will help to. Improve the curriculum and learning so I adopt the changes to this as the 21st century and we have to be flexible.”

Another theme is quality learning which means that schools always make sure that they offer learner-centered teaching-learning process to ensure quality learning among students. They design programs and projects that can definitely hone and develop skills of the students. They encourage to do necessary innovation to go along with 21st century learners. They make necessary improvements and changes to offer innovative, contextualize and localized learning process. Teachers equip themselves with knowledge and skills that will suit with 21st century learners and be prepared to embrace the challenges of the new trends in education. This is validated by instructional supervision of school heads and master teachers. With all these, they are able to give quality learning among students. This is based on the statement of P5 who states that: “We make sure that we have Implemented the different programs or projects and activities which helps our learners develop, develop their skills, develop their personality. So what do we do is that we make projects or we implement projects. We have different programs, projects and activities for the students. We also make sure that we implement those things for the improvement of our students”

This is supported by Tansiri and Bong (2019) who revealed that for schools' personnel, there were supervising and developing the school's teachers by involving them in making decision of the school, sending teachers to follow trainings, giving permission for teachers who want to pursue their degree. Besides, compensation and employee's evaluation. Moreover, De Luna (2021) change should be ultimately geared towards the learners enjoyment of their right to quality education and other equally imperative rights such as the right to be protected from harm and abuse, to be safe and healthy, to play and to have leisure, to freely express their views, and to participate in decision-making processes in accordance to their evolving capacities.

Lastly, the theme adaptability wherein schools are able to adapt on changes and improvements specifically on new trends in education such as in curriculum and innovation. In this 21st century teaching learning process, school and teachers have to adapt with timely and relevant nowadays trends and skills to improve the quality of education that they can offer to the students. Teachers can adapt to it through seminars, trainings and continuous study through graduate school while school can adapt to it through continuous improvement of the school and learning facilities. School and teachers must embrace the changes and innovation in education to be flexible in the 21st century education. Having continuous innovations supported by contextualized and localized materials will surely lead to

successful teaching learning process. This is based on P7 who stated that “We are in the 21st century so we have to adapt what is timely relevant nowadays in education for us to improve the quality of education that we can give to our students. I always tell my teachers and to the students let us embrace the changes and innovation in education we have to be flexible because we are in the 21st century education.”

This result is supported by the study of Acibar and Pepito (2019) School-Based Management is the decentralization of decision-making authority to schools. At the school level, school heads, teachers and pupils work together with the community leaders and local government officials and other stakeholders to improve school performance. Decentralization, in the context of SBM, is the transfer of responsibility for planning school improvement, raising, allocating and managing resources from the central, regional and division levels down to the school sites (DepED Order NO. 230, series 1999).

Best practices that the school perform in accountability and continuous improvement that made their school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM)

The table below shows the statement of the participants and its theme and category. This presents the sharing of the school heads, SBM Coordinators and stakeholders with regards to the best practices that school perform in accountability and continuous improvement that made their school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM)

Table 4. *Best practices that school perform in accountability and continuous improvement that made their school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM)*

Theme	Sub-Theme	Category	Responses
Review and Monitor	Success	Continuous improvement	P1- The continuous monitoring and evaluation of the projects to make sure the success of the projects and it is aligned to the desire results P3- As stakeholder, we join in reviewing and monitoring of the projects. So make sure that the project will be implemented and also for the success of the program. P4- While doing projects, program and activities inside the schools, there must be a checking P7- we practice regular evaluation and provide feedback, we can see the improvement and success of the project P9- we join in planning and monitoring the school project as part of the implementation. We monitor and track the progress. We share our Feedbacks or suggestions during the meeting that can help for the success of projects
Shared Accountability	Collaboration	Accountability	P2- better to have more workforce to accomplish a task the involvement of school members in planning up evaluation had a great impact for the improvement of school project because we shared our suggestions so that we can generate more ways to implement our program, they give their feedback or sides and we open for suggestions of everyone, P5- we have the collaboration or the involvement of all stakeholders and other community members in every step or every program of the school. We invite and inform them to every activity of the school so that they know the plans of the project and how they will contribute for the improvement of the school. P6- We participate in managing and supporting projects and programs. For the schools. I always inform other concerned personnel for the improvement and updates of the schools projects.
Authenticity	Transparency	Accountability	P8- the authenticity when it comes to the project proposal and when it comes to the expenses being put in every budget, there must also be transparency in the finances

For the school heads, the best practices that school perform in accountability and continuous improvement that made their school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM) include: For P1 “It is regularly review and monitor the project and the policies are some of the activities that we perform in continuous improvement and school base management requires review of projects and policies. Through monitors and evaluate. And this is to ensure that projects are aligned and attainable. By the school. We also encourage every Member to share their feedback about the project if there is a need for improvement or making an adjustment. We conduct a regular monitoring of the project to make sure that the project or program we have will success.” According to P4 “While doing projects, program and activities inside the schools, there must be checking. For example, the one particular program for example is already completed. You have to submit report especially the financial aspect of the tracking and post, post it in the transparency. Lastly, for P7 “We practice regular evaluation and provide feedback. We have the practice of regular evaluation, you know we can see the improvement and success of the project. Here we have so many projects that we implemented we conduct monitoring and evaluation to sustain the continuous improvement of our project, because you monitor it, and if you do not monitor it you can not see the improvement, problems might arise, here in our project we always perform monitoring, checking the improvement and also we do not perform it alone, we are with stakeholders that help us in monitoring in our school project.”

For the SBM coordinator, P2 said that “We practiced shared accountability between the school and the community. In shared accountability we promote collaboration to every member of the school like the stakeholders we encouraged them to work together because there are projects or programs that cannot be done alone by the school, we ask the help of our school’s partners. They also share their knowledge to make things happen because sometimes they have a good idea or plan for the improvement of work. they also give constructive feedback that we all know it is very essential to every organization so that we can make adjustment or changes. They also support for the achieving goals because their children will also benefit in this program. For P5, “The involvement of community stakeholders to all the schools plans and projects. We make sure that all, members know the projects. We have the collaboration or the involvement of all stakeholders and other community members in every step or every program of the school. We invite and inform them to every activity of the school so that they know the plans of the project and how they will contribute for the improvement of the school.” Lastly, according to P8 “It is to make sure that there is the authenticity when it comes to the project proposal and when it comes to the expenses being put in every budget. There must also be transparency in the in and out of the finances of every project.”

For the stakeholders, according to P3 “We as community stakeholders. Participate in reviewing and enhancing the accountability system and process so that we can assure that the projects or programs will be implemented and succeed. We join in the deliberation or meeting about the project that need to implement and also uh, we check and visited to see the environment or the improvement.” P6 said that “We participate in managing and supporting projects and programs. For the schools. I always inform other concerned personnel for the improvement and updates of the school’s projects. We can see the improvement and we are happy that we are part of the improvement. we support every school project, the school invited us in planning during the meeting we join in discussion about the implementation of the project up to monitoring because there are times that school more suggestions in planning , we are always here to support the improvement of work, kaya nga every time na mayroon meeting umaattend talaga masaya kasi na maraming nakikiisa sa mga Gawain at para alam kung ano na ba ang update ng project or kung ano pa ang mga kailangan. Lastly, P9 said that “We join in planning and monitoring the school project as part of the implementation. We monitor and track the progress. We share our feedbacks or suggestions during the meeting that can help for the success of projects. We attend meetings to discuss the project updates and on going projects. We join in monitoring to check the progress of every project. sa part na ito nakikita nachecheck naming kung ano ba ang project kung it ba ay ok na, para mamonitor namin ang improvement ng project. as member we also join in monitoring and we share our opinions at iyon naman talaga ang mahalaga.”

In conclusion, the best practices that school perform in accountability and continuous improvement that made their school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM) includes: The first theme is review and monitoring which may lead to the achievement of success and continuous improvement of the school. It is very important that the school consistently monitor and evaluate all the programs and projects. Through this, schools may be able to gather the issues, concerns and problems involving the projects and programs. In addition, they can also ask for feedbacks, comments and suggestions, from this, they can craft solutions and adjust for the achievement of goals and objectives and ensure success. The result of review and monitoring are presented among the stakeholders for feedbacking to gather their comments and suggestions and possibly ask for support to strengthen implementation. This is based on the statement of P7 who shared that: “We practice regular evaluation and provide feedback, monitoring and evaluation are very important. So this will help the improvement of projects, programs on the parts by providing feedback. School and community members who are involved in school-based management. So, we can determine the effectiveness and impact of the programs. For the projects that are implemented so we can use this as evaluation or an assessment to identify the areas for improvement or for the. Improvement of the project itself.”

This is in relation to the study of Kaabi (2019) who stated that the purpose of School – Based Management (SBM) is to improve school performance by making those closest to the delivery of services (teachers, principals, and community) more independent, more involved, and therefore more responsible for their decision with significant support of monitoring and evaluation.

Another theme is shared accountability wherein everyone is given responsibility and tasked to face all the consequence or result. With this shared accountability, collaboration is encouraged which involve all the internal and external stakeholders. With this, everyone take responsibility with their actions and decisions which involve all aspects of school of school process. Everyone has equal putting and all members have shared responsibility and rights to voice out their ideas and take pride in their every actions and decisions of the school process. This is based on the answer of P2 who shared that: “In shared accountability we promote collaboration to every member of the school like the stakeholders we encouraged them to work together because there are projects or programs that can not be done alone by the school, we ask the help of our school’s partners. They also share their knowledge to make things happen because sometimes they have a good idea or plan for the improvement of work. they also give constructive feedback that we all know it is very essential to every organization so that we can make adjustment or changes. They also support for the achieving goals because their children will also benefit in this program. “

As revealed by Bandur (2021) devolution of power and authority to school level can create partnership in participatory school decision making in terms of setting a school mission, shared vision, annual programs, school budget, school textbooks, school buildings, school-based curriculum and even students’ discipline policies. In turn, devolving power and authority to school level has created several changes in schools, including in school culture changes, and increased participation of school communities. These factors have led to the improvements in teaching and learning environments, student achievements and school performance.

Furthermore, the last theme is authenticity wherein schools make sure they practice transparency. School’s projects and programs are authentic and real to everyone. They practice transparency in every projects’ expenses. They prepare financial reports and discuss this among all the members and posted to their transparency board. School heads also consult the BAC for views and opinions and even consult for bidding and needs. In this report, they clearly state the money in and the money out. Budget allocation are discussed and options are presented. Official receipts are presented and explained. This is based on P8 who shared that: “There is the authenticity when it comes to the project proposal and when it comes to the expenses being put. In every budget. There is one of the account one of the best practice practices that. the expenses or a particular project becoming a beginning project, accountability, and there must also be transparency in. The in and. Out of the finances of every of every project, so we never have, we never have a project which is. You when I say authentic, there is a real the realistic expenses and activities being proposed in the school, the activities, the accountability and the transparency.” This result is supported by According to the study of Dacholfany (2022) Schools and the community are given the authority to manage school resources and allocate them according to local priorities, needs, and potential and to be accountable for them, both to the community and the government. However, in reality, with the existing school-based management and community participation, there is still dissatisfaction that arises from the community towards school performance and the low quality of education; this is due to the meager influence of the Principal's Leadership and the Role of the School Committee on the Implementation of School-Based Management.

Best practices that the school perform in management of resources that made their school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM)

The table below shows the statement of the participants and its theme and category. This presents the sharing of the school heads, SBM Coordinators and stakeholders with regards to the best practices that school perform in management of resources that made their school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM).

Table 5. *Best practices that school perform in management of resources that made their school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM)*

Theme	Sub-Theme	Category	Responses
Resource Allocation	Prioritization	Management of resources	P1- resource allocation is one thing that we gave emphasis in install base management because in it involves allocating resources such as budgeting and finances. Based on what is needed or specific. Needs of the school. Before we spend the funds, we perform resource allocation we budget based on what is needed or specific needs of the schools P3- We should know how to budget the funds that we have and of course we should focus what is the important or the priority that is very important in any organization. we have to know our priorities the needs of many P9- we look what is needed because it is important in budgeting. we identified the needs of the school and then sunod ang budgeting P2- we enjoy the stakeholders. They are always engaged in decision making. We involve the community on how to successfully allocate and utilize funds, especially with regards to. MOEE. they give assistance or funds for the schools and sometime they donate painting and construction materials.
	Assistance		
Stake holders Involvement		Management of resources	P8 - we ask for the support of the stakeholders, the CSR or the the customer support. the, the customer social responsibility. All Industries that we have around the school, we ask for the support because the school must be must also be benefited by their existence. P6- Perform management of resources. The management of resources, we participate every time we have a meeting like planning and resource programming and support We are invited to the school’s activity like liquidation and liquidation of funds. We also share our opinions in managing that can help the school for the utilization of funds. P9- We are here to help the school we join in meeting about budgeting. Because budgeting is important, in applying strategy in the project we join in budgeting like canvassing the prices of materials we give possible supplier that can save money for the project, laki kasi ng matitipid alam mo iyon pag maraming option, kaya nag strategize din kami sa budgeting.
	Support		
proper utilization of resources	Transparency	Management of resources	P4- The proper utilization of resources, so the main. There is transparency. We have here transparency board. P5- know the transparency. So everything about the resources that we have in our school is very transparent from the MOOE to the local fund. It is posted on the Transparency Board, how it is utilized. P7- in our school we perform transparency we apply it to everything. Once we have school project we want to be open to all school members the stakeholders and parents that we have school project that these are the budget and expenses that we have.
Income Generating Project	Segregation	Management of Resources	P8- To the IGP where I'm coming with the income generating project in particular is the trash this trash segregation,

Based on the result, according to the school heads the best practices that school perform in management of resources that made their school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM) include: P1 shared that “It involves allocating resources such as budgeting and finances. Based on what is needed or specific. Needs of the school. We all know that the school has many extra expenses that we need to make sure the budget or fund we spend will be used. Before we spend the funds, we perform resource allocation we budget based on what is needed or specific needs of the schools because you now we have limited resources we have to think that the program or project we do are needed by the school or students.” P4 stated that “The proper utilization of resources, so the main. There is transparency. We have here transparency board. There are. Resources financial resources inside the school first is the maintenance and operating expenses, second is the local funds. In in the utilization of maintenance and other operating expenses, person and school person that must be informed on how what Oh. Why it is the money Is utilized and then following the following the correct process Of. Spending the government plan.” Lastly, P7 shared that “That transparent is essential to know if the funds are rigorously utilized. In an appropriate program or any. Activities in the school. So we do disclosure of funds. We spend the budget, expenses, stores, school staff or teachers and communities, stakeholders like parents and students. So with this activity, raise your information to everyone and all members are updated on how we spend the various for fund. So best transparency is important to build this to everyone.”

For the SBM coordinators, P2 said that “they are part in decision making of the school the BOD and other stakeholders. We all know we need to budget the funds that we have for the schools and sometime it is hard to allocate and utilize funds appropriately to what is priority or really needed. They also share their practices in their work every time we have a meeting they express their opinions to the group meeting. Like for example in the implementation of school projects we have to allocate funds but because they are part of the school they assistance or funds for the schools and sometime they donate painting and constructing materials we all know that we have limited budget in MOOE in that way it will lessen the costing or budget of the project and we can use the remaining funds or to other projects.” For P5, “For the management of resources, it's very basic know the transparency. So everything about the resources that we have in our school is very transparent from the MOOE to the local fund. It is posted on the Transparency Board, how it is utilized. So we always have the. Updated liquidation of the. Resources, so it's not. It's easy for us, you know, to, to relate and to read, to see what is really inside or what's behind this or the local fund that being utilized by the school.” While for P8, “how to support every project that cannot be provided by the resources of the school. To the IGP where I'm coming with the income generating project in particular is the trash this trash segregation, So we have the we have income in that particular project that can provide other expenses. Of the school. And then, of course, we ask for the support of the stakeholders, the CSR or the the customer support. the, the customer social responsibility. All Industries that we have around the school, we ask for the support because the school must be must also be benefited by their existence. So we have those kind of Steps for us to provide all those things that we need that cannot be provided, particularly by the MOOE of the school.”

For the stakeholders, according to P3 “, we should know how to budget the funds that we have and of course we should focus what is the important or the priority that is very important in any organization. We are involve din budget of the school funds like planning to have a project we make sure that we have enough money for construction, as our part we help the school in budgeting. we have to know our priorities the needs of many, para makapag budget tayo at malaan ng pondo, we need to identify the needs for resource allocation, because in school you have so many expenses you have to divide the funds for every project.” For P6, “we participate every time we have a meeting like planning and resource programming and support We are invited to the schools activity like liquidation and liquidation of funds. We also share our opinions in managing that can help the school for the utilization of funds. As our contribution in the school improvement we joined in budgeting of the school we help the school to allocate funds for the program and also we share how the school can save money for the project.” Lastly. according to P9 “We are here to help the school we join in meeting about budgeting. Because budgeting is important, in applying strategy in the project we join in budgeting like canvassing the prices of materials we give possible supplier that can save money for the project, laki kasi ng matitipid alam mo iyon pag maraming option, kaya nag strategize din kami sa budgeting. At dapat everybody knows the budget to use at lalong higit is the manpower , who will work , number of working days at data of implementation.”

It can be implied that the best practices that school perform in management of resources that made their school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM) includes: The first theme is resource allocation which means they strictly allocate budget on the needs of the school and value prioritization. School heads, teachers and stakeholders convene to discuss the needs and urgency of the resources depending on the urgency of programs and projects before they decide for the final budget allocation. With these, they can adjust and allocate their funds wisely which mean they are able to maximize the means that they have. This is important in following the principle of urgency, relevance and needs of the school. This is based on the statement of P1 who shared that: It involves allocating resources such as budgeting and finances. Based on what is needed or specific. Needs of the school. We all know that the school has many extra expenses that we need to make sure the budget or fund we spend. Will be used. Will be used for the improvement of the school or students and proper of course proper utilization of funds should be practiced and what is really needed.

In support Faubert (2019) stated that it is to important to consider the role education finance leaders in handling finances to maximize resources ot provide the needs of the school and validate the expenses of the institution and what types of evidence they are using, how they are being employed and how much priority is given to each.

The next theme is stakeholders' involvement wherein schools involve their stakeholders. Schools extend their channel with their community by involving all the possible external stakeholders in planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation. Through this, stakeholders willingly give assistance to the school. They help teachers in their projects, donate materials or even offer time and skills for manual work. They make sure that they support the school. They attend meetings, listening for liquidation and even help in budgeting by sharing their opinions and suggestions. They even help in canvassing, sharing strategies and brainstorming for ways to budget the funds. They give comments, suggestions and feedbacks all throughout of the process. This is based on P9 who shared that: As stakeholder we make a way to implement the project by knowing what is needed of the school. We are here to help the school we join in meeting about budgeting. Because budgeting is important, in applying strategy in the project we join in budgeting like canvassing the prices of materials we give possible supplier that can save money for the project, laki kasi ng matitipid alam mo iyon pag maraming option, kaya nag strategize din kami sa budgeting. At dapat everybody knows the budget to use at lalong higit is the manpower, who will work, number of working days at data of implementation.

This is in accordance with Warsi (2019), states that leadership and governance requires the input of different stakeholders such as parents, teachers, school heads, administration, and school boards. Stakeholders are important as they can take leadership responsibilities, or lend voice to ideas, opinions, and perspectives. It should be understood that the role of every stakeholder is crucial for the development of an education empire.

Moreover, the next theme is proper utilization of resources wherein schools strictly follow proper utilization of resources. This means that school truly allot their funds and resources to the urgent needs of the school. This is supported by their practice of real transparency. They discuss the budget, the money in, the money out, among all the people involve even with the stakeholders. The financial reports are discussed and even posted in transparency board. This is based on the statement of P7 who shared that: In transparency, it is one thing that we need to remember in management of resources, in our we strictly implement in every project that we have. We have to be open to everyone, the school members and stakeholders how do we spend the resources that we have and it is essential to every organization. We do the disclosure of expense, all members of school and stakeholders, parents are part of the liquidation process we invite them in our school meeting to discuss how we spend the budget and they participate in auditing of funds if it is correct, then during the meeting we explain the expenses and if it clear, we report it the expenses to all concerns and we print the copy of expenses to make it transparent for record copy of project expenses and lastly the posting of expenses in our school disclosure board to see it by everyone.

The areas of effective leadership and budget allocation have no or little authority. Further, in terms of participation, the staff in SBM participate more in areas where they have more authority than in areas where they do not have authority since other members. (Kaabi, 2019).

Last theme is income generating project. Since most of the time, schools struggles for budget, schools make way to have extra budget or think of projects that will generate funds which can be utilized by the school in their other needs. With this, there are some schools who look for Income Generating Project like recycling, segregation, fund raising and the like. For example, the waste segregation involves gathering trash that can be recycled and come up with other products that can be sold and some can be source of income like plastics and papers by selling them in junk shops. This is based on the statement of P8 who shared that: So every school, of course, we have an ending. We have an end. Necessities and those necessities cannot be provided at all. So the school is projecting and thinking of ways on how to, on how to support every project that cannot be provided by the resources of the school. To the IGP where I'm coming with the income generating project in particular is the trash this trash segregation, So we have the we have income in that particular project that can provide other expenses. Of the school.

This result is in accordance with Agustina et al & Tobari, (2021) school principals are responsible for influencing the work environment in the following ways: 1) controlling the school's physical environment; 2) establishing an atmosphere and working environment; 3) a changing culture in the school The principal should be able to create a comfortable environment by mobilizing all school members to create and maintain order, safety, shade, and cleanliness as the physical organizer of the school environment.

School-based management (SBM) is a new paradigm in education, which provides autonomy at the school level (community involvement) within the framework of national education policies. Autonomy is given so that schools are more flexible in managing resources in accordance with priority needs kebutuhan (Arar & Abu-Romi, 2016). Community involvement is intended so that they better understand, assist, and control the management of education (Bandur et al., 2021).

Conclusions

The study can be concluded that: The best practices performed in leadership and governance that made the school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM) includes schools planning. They set clear vision and define goals and objectives followed by strategic planning for future projects through collaboration where everyone has equal chance to share and contribute their ideas, comments, suggestions and feedbacks which could be a basis for improvements since school will be able to reflect and evaluate the programs and projects of the school. As the school pioneered their programs and projects, it is very important that they continuously monitor and evaluate all the projects to ensure success or adjust if problems and issues arise. With regards to governance, they involve of community, internal and external stakeholders through shared governance wherein everyone holds

responsibility and contributes to the progress of the school.

The best practices that school perform in curriculum and learning that made them standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM) includes collaborative decision making that involve stakeholders or different organization in all the activities, programs and projects of the school specially if it is about curriculum. The decisions of the school become more effective and stronger through the help of the people around them because of their shared discussion, comments, suggestions and feedback. Stakeholders give assistance to schools. They give their time and service, donate, help teachers in projects like in reading and basic math lessons. Furthermore, the schools ensure implementation of the required curriculum practice delegation of task With the strict monitoring and evaluation, they can also check if everyone is able to adapt in all the trends and innovations of 21st century learning. Schools always make sure that they offer quality Learning.

The best practices that school perform in accountability and continuous improvement that made their school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM) includes review and monitoring to achieve success of continuous improvement. Through this, schools may be able to gather the issues, concerns, problems and feedbacks involving the projects and programs to craft solutions and adjust for the achievement of goals and objectives and ensure success. Another best practice of school is shared accountability. With this, everyone take responsibility with their actions and decisions. Furthermore, schools practice project authenticity. They practice transparency in every projects' expenses.

The best practices that school perform in management of resources that made their school standout and reach the advanced phase level of practice of School-Based Management (SBM) includes strict resource allocation which means they value prioritization. With these, they can adjust and allocate their funds wisely. Other schools involve their stakeholder. They help teachers for their projects, donate materials or even offer time and skills for manual work. They attend meetings, listening for liquidation and even help in budgeting by sharing their opinions and suggestions. They even help in canvassing, sharing strategies and brainstorming for ways to budget the funds. Moreover, schools strictly follow proper utilization of resources. They practice real transparency. Since most schools struggles for budget, schools make way to have extra budget. There are some schools who look for Income Generating Project.

Based from the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were hereby suggested: Division Supervisor may consider to offer refresher courses about SBM and any other needed related skills for handling SBM; More detailed guidelines and centralized assistance for school heads and SBM Coordinators; Schools Division may also offer Stakeholders convention to strengthen stakeholders participation; School heads may be consistent in conducting team building among teachers and stakeholders to strengthen their relationship and bonding since they always involve stakeholders in all aspects of the school; For the future researcher to look into considerations the limitations and variables which are not discussed in the paper.

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